

New Indicators for the Direct HEDTA Titration of Ferric Ions

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The working conditions for the use of protocatechuic acid, 3-hydroxy 2-naphthoic acid and tiron as indicators for the direct HEDTA titration of ferric ions are reported. These indicators give a sharp colour change at the end point and can be used for microtitration of iron, the lowest permissible concentration being 0.056 mg/ml. A large number of diverse ions are tolerated. A procedure has been suggested for the determination of ferric ions when present alone in synthetic solutions, an ore and pharmaceuticals.

WHILE a number of substances investigated as indicators for the direct EDTA titration of ferric ions, no substances have been reported so far for the direct titration of HEDTA with ferric ions. The present article reports the use of protocatechuic acid, 3-hydroxy 2-naphthoic acid and tiron as indicators for the direct HEDTA titration of ferric ions. Protocatechuic acid and tiron give green colour with ferric ions, whereas 3-hydroxy 2-naphthoic acid gives a blue colour. When such a solution was titrated with HEDTA, the characteristic green or blue colour was discharged and at the end point, there was a sudden change to yellow. If a solution of HEDTA was titrated with ferric ions, there was a change from colourless to light green with tiron and protocatechuic acid and from colourless to light blue with 3-hydroxy 2-naphthoic acid.

Experimental

Ferric Nitrate Solution :

A stock solution of ferric nitrate (0.1 M) was prepared by dissolving 40.38 g of ferric nitrate nonahydrate in distilled water and making upto one litre. It was standardised gravimetrically as ferric oxide.

HEDTA solution :

A stock solution of 0.01 M HEDTA was prepared by dissolving 2.78 g. of HEDTA in distilled water on heating and making upto one litre.

Indicator solutions :

1% solution were prepared from pure samples of the reagents by dissolving the requisite amount in 95% alcohol. The solutions were stable upto four weeks.

Metal solutions :

To study the interference of various foreign ions in the estimation of iron(III) with HEDTA, the corresponding analar quality of salts were taken and their 0.2 M solutions were prepared in distilled water.

Suggested procedure :

Take an aliquot of solution containing ferric ions, adjust the pH to 1.0-2.0 and add four drops of a 1% solution of the indicator. Titrate against standard HEDTA solution to a deep yellow colour.

Effect of pH :

It was found that when HEDTA solution was taken in burette, accurate results were obtained in the pH range 1.0-2.8, at 0.01 M and 0.005 M concentrations of ferric ions. In case of 0.001 M concentrations of ferric ions accurate results were obtained in the pH range of 2.0 - 2.8. Outside these ranges, the accuracy of titration decreased. Further it should also be noted that at pH values less than 1.5, the colour intensity of ferric complex of the indicator decreased. It was thus advisable to add a higher amount of indicator in the pH range below 1.5.

If the ferric solution was taken in the burette accurate results were obtained over a wide pH range, i.e. to 1.0-9.0. However, the former process is more satisfactory because the colour change is more perceptible.

Effect of Indicator Concentration :

Titrations were carried out with different proportions of the indicator and it was found that an addition of 4 drops of 1% indicator solution in ethanol to 5 ml of titre solution gave accurate and sharp end point.

Effect of ferric ion concentration :

0.01 M, 0.005 M, 0.001 M and 0.0005M solutions of ferric ion were titrated with HEDTA using the suggested indicators. At 0.0005 M concentration of iron, the end point was not very sharp. However the titration of 1.0 ml volume of 0.001 M ferric nitrate could be accurately performed with a sharp end point. Thus microtitration of ferric ions with HEDTA is feasible with these indicators.

Effect of Temperature :

Titration were carried out at three temperature ranges 0-5°, 30-35° and 55-60°. It was necessary to add slightly more indicator at lower temperature. Accurate results could be obtained at all the temperatures investigated.

Effect of Foreign Ions :

Synthetic solutions containing 2.8 mg iron(III) were titrated at pH 1.0 and 2.0 It was found that 100 fold amount of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, La³⁺, Ca²⁺, Be²⁺, UO₂²⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻, 4 fold amount of Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Sr²⁺, 2 fold amount of Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Al³⁺, Mn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺, and equal amount of Pb²⁺, Ag⁺, Cr³⁺ and HCO₃⁻ could be tolerated (i.e. error <1%) phosphate, fluoride oxalate, carbonate, iodide, thorium and zirconium interfered at all levels.

Analysis of Pharmaceuticals Containing Iron :

The suggested procedure was applied to the analysis of pharmaceuticals containing iron in the form of colloidal iron hydroxide, ferrous gluconate, ferrous fumarate and ferrous sulphate.

Liquid drugs containing ferrous sulphate or ferric hydroxide were diluted with distilled water, and 2.0 ml conc. HNO₃ was added. The mixture was heated for 10-15 minutes and after cooling, diluted to 100 ml.

Tablets or capsules of drugs containing ferrous sulphate, ferrous fumarate or ferrous gluconate were treated with 10 ml conc. HNO₃ and 2 ml. HClO₄. The mixture was evaporated to dryness. The residue was diluted to 50 ml aliquots of the dilute solution were used for titration. Results are given in table 2.

Ore :

2 g. of bauxite ore was fused with 10.0 g. of fusionmixture and treated with conc. HCl. 2 ml nitric acid was then added to oxidise ferrous ions to ferric ions, silica was filtered and the filtrate was diluted to 100 ml. 5.0 ml. diluted solution was used to estimate iron. The expected iron content was 2.86% Fe₂O₃ while the iron content found by above procedure was 2.8% Fe₂O₃.

TABLE—1 ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS

pH of titration : 1.0 Fe ³⁺ taken (mg)	Foreign ions (mg)		Tiron	Concentration of HEDTA : 0.01 M	
				Protocatechuic acid	Fe ³⁺ found (mg) 3-hydroxy 2-naphthoic acid
2.8	Ca ²⁺ 7.0,	Sr ²⁺ 8.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	Ca ²⁺ 8.0,	Ba ²⁺ 7.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	Mg ²⁺ 2.5,	Pb ²⁺ 1.25	2.75	2.8	2.8
2.8	Zn ²⁺ 2.5,	Mg ²⁺ 2.5	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	Cd ²⁺ 2.0,	Be ²⁺ 25.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	K ⁺ 17.5,	NH ₄ ⁺ 22.5	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	La ³⁺ 25.0,	Cs ⁺ 15.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	SO ₄ ²⁻ 30.0,	NO ₃ ⁻ 10.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	Cl ⁻ 25.0,	Br ⁻ 25.0	2.8	2.8	2.8
2.8	Co ²⁺ 2.5,	Ni ²⁺ 2.5	2.8	2.8	2.8

TABLE—2 ANALYSIS OF DRUGS CONTAINING IRON BY DIRECT TITRATION WITH HEDTA

Drug trade name	State of the drug	Manufacture	Active constituent of the drug	Fe ³⁺ expected (g)	Fe ³⁺ Indicator Tiron	Found (g)	
						Indicator Protocatechuic acid	Indicator 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid
Polycytol	Tablet	Alembic Chemicals	Ferrous sulphate (dried)	0.195	0.194	0.194	0.194
Fersolate	Tablet	Glaxo Laboratory	Ferrous sulphate (dried)	0.195	0.194	0.191	0.194
Iberol	Tablet	Abbott Laboratory	Ferrous sulphate (hydrated)	0.525	0.522	0.522	0.522
Iberoliquid	Syrup	Abbott Laboratory	Ferrous sulphate (hydrated)	0.131	0.130	0.130	0.130
Livogen	Capsule	British Drug House	Ferrous fumarate	0.150	0.146	0.146	0.146
Ferrolindione	Tablet	Indopharma ⁷ Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous fumarate	0.200	0.197	0.193	0.197
Microfer	Tablet	Naphtha Pharmaceuticals	Ferrous gluconate	0.195	0.194	0.192	0.190
Tonoferon drops	Syrup	East India Pharmaceutical Works	Colloidal hydroxide	0.050	0.046	0.047	0.047

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The above procedure was applied to the determination of ferric ions in synthetic solutions. Results are given in Table 1.